

Study of the Deuterium Concentration in Lithium Deuteride: Tritium Fusion on Deuterium

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Abstract

This work presents a comprehensive study of the deuterium concentration in lithium deuteride (LiD) with the aim of optimizing tritium fusion on deuterium via the $t + d \rightarrow \alpha + n$ channel. Monte Carlo simulations, performed using GEANT4 v10.2, were employed to investigate various geometries and material compositions. The study examines configurations such as a 30 mm disk used for initial optimization, a spherical shell surrounding a beryllium sphere for complete process evaluation, and thin-layer structures composed of alternating LiD and ultra-dense deuterium (D***). Different mixtures, including one with an average density between LiD and D*** (referred to as “mixture m.”) and various LiD-D*** volume fractions, were analyzed over a range of D*** densities.

Results indicate that for the selected configuration “mixture m.” with a D*** density of 10 g/cm^3 , the number of $t + d$ interactions is maximized while still allowing a significant neutron flux to exit the fuel cell. Additionally, preliminary studies on thin-layer geometries and triton acceleration suggest further optimization. Although the simulation developed in GEANT4 version (v10.2) with triton interactions modelled with parameterized theoretical cross sections appears overly pessimistic compared to experimental data, the implementation of experimental cross sections in GEANT4 v10.3 is anticipated to yield more favorable predictions. These findings provide essential insights into the design and engineering of fuel materials for tritium fusion.

1 Introduction

The purpose of this third phase of the work is to study the deuterium concentration in an appropriate layer of lithium deuteride and ultra-dense deuterium, in order to optimize the process of tritium fusion on deuterium via the channel $t + d \rightarrow \alpha + n$. Different geometries were considered, and in the configuration selected as the best choice, a simulation was performed with 10^2 times the number of input particles to confirm, with high statistics, the previous result.

2 Materials and Methods

The study of the interaction processes of neutrons and tritons in lithium deuteride and ultra-dense deuterium, with the subsequent optimization of the fuel cell for tritium fusion, was carried out using Monte Carlo simulations based on the GEANT4 toolkit [1] **version 10.2**, modeling, as specified in the Report on GEANT4 cross sections [2], triton interactions with parameterized cross sections.

2.1 The Geometry

The geometries used are:

- a 30 mm thick disk: used for selecting the best configuration;
- a spherical shell, surrounding the beryllium sphere (with a radius of 200 mm) optimized in the first part of this work [3], used to test the complete process.

The materials used are LiD and ultra-dense deuterium (hereafter referred to as D***) in various compositions, namely:

- a mixture with an average density between that of LiD and D***, hereafter referred to as “mixture m.”;
- a mixture with LiD-D*** volume fractions of: 9-1, 14-1, 19-1, 24-1, 49-1, 74-1, 99-1;
- thin layers made of $1\mu\text{m}$ of D*** adjacent to LiD layers of $25\mu\text{m}$ and $60\mu\text{m}$.

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Figure 1: Graphical output of two simulation events: on the left, for the geometry with the disk, and on the right, for the case of the spherical shell surrounding the beryllium sphere.

For each of these configurations, the following densities in g/cm^3 were considered for D^{***} : 10^0 , 10^1 , 10^2 , 10^3 , 10^4 , and 10^5 .

Figure 1 shows the outputs of two events: on the left, the case of the disk hit by a thermal neutron, and on the right, the case of the beryllium sphere surrounded by the spherical shell of $LiD+D^{***}$. The image also displays the neutron tracks (in green).

2.2 The Physics

From a physics standpoint, it is crucial to emphasize that the GEANT4 version used for these simulations is 10.2, with the triton interaction modeled using parameterized theoretical cross sections.

However, experimental data-driven cross sections, the G4TENDL1.0, have recently been implemented in GEANT4 to describe the interactions much more accurately, as extensively illustrated in the ad-hoc report on cross sections (for further details, see [2]). These cross-sections are available in GEANT4 version 10.3, which was released on February 28. This latest version was initially used by us for this third phase of the work; unfortunately, however, during the course of this study, we noticed some anomalies that revealed the presence of a bug in version 10.3 regarding the treatment of tritons. This bug has been reported to the GEANT4 developer responsible for this specific aspect. This issue forced us to step back and revert to version 10.2, which has been extensively tested and is fully operational. The remaining problem, therefore, is that this entire study is based on triton cross sections that are profoundly pessimistic or rather, completely insensitive to triton reactions over most of the energy range of interest, particularly with regard to the $t+d$ interaction, which is of vital importance for the fusion process. In Figure 2, we compare the experimental curve (in red) with the parameterized theoretical curve we used with GEANT4 v.10.2 (in black) for the $t+d$ interaction.

Figure 2: Cross section of the $t+d$ interaction: the experimental curve is shown in red (according to the ENDF database [5]), while the parameterized theoretical cross section used in GEANT4 v.10.2 is shown in black.

3 Data and Analysis

The study is divided into three parts:

1. The Mixture;
2. The Thin Layers;
3. Triton Acceleration.

which are now described in detail.

3.1 First Part: The Mixture

For each of the $LiD+D^{***}$ compositions previously detailed, a 30 mm thick disk was generated, and 10^6 primary events of thermal neutrons (monochromatic with an energy of 0.025 eV) were fired at it. The results obtained are presented in Table 1. In this table, the cases selected as the most interesting are highlighted in yellow, based on a threshold established as a number of $t+d$ interactions ≥ 250 ; in all cases where the number of counts, within their statistical error, is compatible with this threshold, the selection criterion is satisfied. Looking at the table, it is evident that, since the statistical error for counts of 220 units is 20 and for counts of 230 units is 30, all cases with a number of $t+d$ events ≥ 230 are compatible with the selection criterion. Since all the selected cases are equivalent within statistical fluctuations, they were reexamined with a statistics 10 times higher in order to capture any differences. The results obtained in this second set of simulations are presented in Table 2.

As can be seen, even with this improved statistics, many configurations remain equivalent within their error, particularly those with a number of $t+d$ counts between 2560 and 2720. This latter value, which is the maximum obtained in this second set of simulations, also corresponds, within this second set, to the lowest density value, namely $10^1 g/cm^3$, compared to $10^2 g/cm^3$, $10^3 g/cm^3$, and $10^4 g/cm^3$ for the

other cases (see Table 2): the corresponding configuration (highlighted in green) is “*mixture m.*”. It is therefore decided to opt for this latter configuration, as it is certainly less complicated and less costly to achieve a deuterium density of $10^1 g/cm^3$ rather than $10^2 g/cm^3$, $10^3 g/cm^3$, or $10^4 g/cm^3$.

This trend in the data, where initially the counts of $t+d$ interactions increase with the density of D^{***} , and then begin to decrease (for densities greater than $10^3 g/cm^3$), is due to the fact that a high D^{***} density is required to favor the tritium fusion reaction; however, if the density exceeds a certain level, the neutron capture interactions by deuterium increase significantly at the expense of the inelastic collision interaction on Li-6.

Now, while the neutron interaction on Li-6 produces tritium at 2.72 MeV, the capture by D produces low-energy tritium (below 60 keV), which is therefore below the threshold for the $t+d$ fusion interaction (this is also the case with the correct experimental cross section; see the red curve in Figure 2).

The trend of the contributions of these two interactions to tritium production as a function of the D^{***} density is illustrated in Figure 3.

For the selected configuration:

- *mixture m.*;
- deuterium density of $10^1 g/cm^3$.

a study was carried out with the complete geometry, that is, a fuel cell composed of concentric spheres (a spherical shell surrounding the beryllium sphere) with a monochromatic neutron source of 14.1 MeV at the center, to evaluate whether modifying the mixture thickness would allow a greater number of neutrons to exit the fuel cell. The results obtained are shown in Table 3 and in Figures 4, 5, and 6 for thicknesses of 30, 20, and 10 mm.

Based on the results obtained, it was decided to reduce the mixture thickness from 30 to 20 mm, in order to allow a larger number of neutrons to exit the fuel cell and feed the potential subsequent stage, without excessively sacrificing the number of $t+d$ interactions.

With this selected configuration, with a 20 mm thick spherical shell of $LiD+D^{***}$, a simulation was carried out with statistics 100 times higher: 10^8 primary events of monochromatic 14.1 MeV neutrons generated from the center of the beryllium sphere. The results obtained are as follows (in this case as well, the quoted statistical error is 1.64σ , C.L. 90%):

- Produced tritons: **185500000 ± 20000**

- $t+d$ interactions: **50100 ± 400**
- Outgoing neutrons: **11470000 ± 6000**
 - of which from $t+d$: **6680 ± 130**

These high-statistics results have confirmed what was previously obtained with 10^6 primary events, as presented in Table 3.

3.2 Second Part: Preliminary Study on Thin Layers

A preliminary study was carried out on a geometry consisting of thin layers of LiD and D^{***} , placed adjacent to each other. The layer configurations considered are:

1. 2 layers: $60\mu m$ of LiD + $1\mu m$ of D^{***} ;
2. 2 layers: $25\mu m$ of LiD + $1\mu m$ of D^{***} ;
3. 8 layers: $25\mu m$ of LiD + $1\mu m$ of D^{***} , replicated four times;

All three cases were repeated for all the previously considered D^{***} densities.

For each simulation, 10^6 primary events of thermal neutrons were generated, fired against the first layer (LiD).

The results obtained are shown in Table 4 and in Figure 7.

From the results obtained in this preliminary phase, it is evident that the thin-layer configuration could also be a viable approach for producing the fuel material. Obviously, a different number of double layers in sequence would be necessary, which, however, requires a separate study to clarify both the number and the physico-chemical characteristics.

3.3 Third Part: Preliminary Study on Triton Acceleration

A preliminary study on triton acceleration was carried out: for various densities of D^{***} , the energy of the triton, used in this case as the primary incident particle, was modified. The geometric configuration used was that of the “*mixture m.*”. The study was then repeated for the configuration selected in the optimization performed in the previous section 3.1 of this report, namely *mixture m.* with a D^{***} density of $10 g/cm^3$. The results obtained are presented in Table 5.

From these results, it can be seen that if the triton is accelerated, this leads to a rapid increase in the frequency of $t+d$ interactions as the triton energy increases, given the cross sections currently in use.

$\rho_{D***} = 10^0 g/cm^3$		$\rho_{D***} = 10^1 g/cm^3$		$\rho_{D***} = 10^2 g/cm^3$	
Configuration	# t+d	Configuration	# t+d	Configuration	# t+d
mixture m.	190 ± 20	mixture m.	270 ± 30	mixture m.	250 ± 30
9-1	111 ± 17	9-1	180 ± 20	9-1	250 ± 30
14-1	78 ± 14	14-1	170 ± 20	14-1	250 ± 30
19-1	101 ± 16	19-1	160 ± 20	19-1	260 ± 30
24-1	75 ± 14	24-1	124 ± 18	24-1	220 ± 20
49-1	99 ± 16	49-1	105 ± 17	49-1	230 ± 30
74-1	71 ± 14	74-1	116 ± 18	74-1	200 ± 20
99-1	93 ± 16	99-1	113 ± 17	99-1	170 ± 20

$\rho_{D***} = 10^3 g/cm^3$		$\rho_{D***} = 10^4 g/cm^3$		$\rho_{D***} = 10^5 g/cm^3$	
Configuration	# t+d	Configuration	# t+d	Configuration	# t+d
mixture m.	160 ± 20	mixture m.	64 ± 13	mixture m.	18 ± 7
9-1	250 ± 30	9-1	150 ± 20	9-1	71 ± 14
14-1	280 ± 30	14-1	180 ± 20	14-1	83 ± 15
19-1	260 ± 30	19-1	190 ± 20	19-1	70 ± 14
24-1	250 ± 30	24-1	230 ± 30	24-1	83 ± 15
49-1	280 ± 30	49-1	210 ± 20	49-1	139 ± 19
74-1	290 ± 30	74-1	250 ± 30	74-1	136 ± 19
99-1	270 ± 30	99-1	240 ± 30	99-1	170 ± 20

Table 1: Results of the first set of simulations, performed for all configurations with 10^6 primary thermal neutron events (monochromatic with an energy of 0.025 eV). The considered error is the random statistical uncertainty at 1.64σ , 90% confidence level. The most interesting cases, highlighted in yellow, were further investigated with ten times higher statistics (see Table 2).

ρ_{D***} [g/cm ³]	Configuration	t+d [#]
10 ¹	mixture m.	2720 ± 80
10 ²	mixture m.	2490 ± 80
10 ²	9-1	2630 ± 80
10 ²	14-1	2580 ± 80
10 ²	19-1	2570 ± 80
10 ²	49-1	2230 ± 80
10 ³	9-1	2510 ± 80
10 ³	14-1	2630 ± 80
10 ³	19-1	2710 ± 80
10 ³	24-1	2710 ± 80
10 ³	49-1	2670 ± 80
10 ³	74-1	2710 ± 80
10 ³	99-1	2570 ± 80
10 ⁴	24-1	1920 ± 80
10 ⁴	74-1	2410 ± 80
10 ⁴	99-1	2490 ± 80

Table 2: Results of the second set of simulations, performed for all cases with 10^7 primary thermal neutron events (monochromatic with an energy of 0.025 eV). The considered error is the random statistical uncertainty at 1.64σ , 90% confidence level. The selected case is highlighted in green.

Thickness [mm]	Produced Tritons [#]	t+d [#]	n_{out} [#]	n from t+d [#]
30	1935000 ± 2000	510 ± 40	42300 ± 300	24 ± 10
20	1855000 ± 2000	470 ± 40	115000 ± 600	55 ± 16
10	1674000 ± 2000	450 ± 40	282000 ± 900	112 ± 20

Table 3: As the thickness varies (given in the first column), the table reports the number of tritons produced (second column), the number of $t+d$ interactions (third column), the number of neutrons exiting the fuel cell n_{out} (fourth column), and how many of them originate from the $t+d$ interaction (fifth column). The considered error is the random statistical uncertainty at 1.64σ , 90% confidence level.

Figure 3: Energy spectra of tritons produced in the $\text{LiD} + \text{D}^{***}$ interaction. The peak populated by neutron capture on deuterium is shown in red, while the peak populated by inelastic neutron interaction on Li-6 is shown in blue.

Figure 4: Radial position where the produced tritons stop, in the case of a LiD+D*** thickness of 30 mm. All tritons are shown in blue, while those entering the $t+d$ channel are shown in red.

Figure 5: Radial position where the produced tritons stop, in the case of a LiD+D*** thickness of 20 mm. All tritons are shown in blue, while those entering the $t+d$ channel are shown in red.

Figure 6: Radial position where the produced tritons stop, in the case of a LiD+D*** thickness of 10 mm. All tritons are shown in blue, while those entering the $t+d$ channel are shown in red.

Configuration	$\rho_{D^{***}} [g/cm^3]$					
	10^0	10^1	10^2	10^3	10^4	10^5
1	65 ± 13	90 ± 16	75 ± 14	93 ± 16	78 ± 14	64 ± 13
2	62 ± 13	93 ± 16	86 ± 15	95 ± 16	73 ± 14	46 ± 11
3	71 ± 14	110 ± 17	98 ± 16	127 ± 18	81 ± 15	43 ± 11

Table 4: As the configuration with thin layers varies, the number of interactions $t+d$ is reported for the different values of the density of D^{***} . The error considered is the random statistical error at 1.64σ , 90% confidence level.

Figure 7: Comparison between the three thin-layer configurations regarding the number of $t+d$ interactions as a function of the D^{***} density.

Triton energy [MeV]	$\rho_{D^{***}} [g/cm^3]$	t+d [#]	$\rho_{D^{***}} [g/cm^3]$	t+d [#]
3	1	230 ± 30	10	330 ± 30
7	2.5	1850 ± 70	10	2220 ± 80
15	5	8190 ± 150	10	8560 ± 150
30	10	23800 ± 300	10	23800 ± 300
50	20	48500 ± 400	10	47700 ± 400
100	40	106900 ± 500	10	105500 ± 500

Table 5: Number of $t+d$ interactions as a function of triton energy, obtained in two LiD+ D^{***} mixing configurations: the first with varying D^{***} densities and the second with a fixed density of $10 g/cm^3$ (optimized configuration in section 3.1 of this report). The considered error is the random statistical error at 1.64σ , 90% confidence level.

4 Conclusions

Based on the results obtained in this study, through the execution of several Monte Carlo simulations with increasing statistics (10^6 , 10^7 , and 10^8 primary events generated), using the GEANT4 toolkit, we can conclude the following: a potential material for tritium fusion fuel consists of a mixture of lithium deuteride (LiD) and ultra-dense deuterium (D^{***}) in a 1:1 volume ratio, with a D^{***} density of 10 g/cm^3 . The choice of this configuration, among the 48 studied, is motivated by the objective of maximizing the number of $t+d$ interactions occurring in the fuel material; however, among configurations yielding similar results, the one expected to be less demanding from an engineering and economic perspective was preferred.

In addition to optimizing the LiD+D^{***} mixture, two preliminary studies were conducted on:

- A fuel configuration with alternating thin layers of LiD and D^{***};
- Triton acceleration during its passage through the fuel.

The results of these studies, although still in an early stage, have provided useful insights into additional approaches that could be explored to enhance fusion self-sustainability.

However, it is essential to emphasize once again a critical aspect in interpreting the results of this report: this entire study is based on a modeling of triton interactions using the physics implemented in GEANT4 v.10.2 with parameterized theoretical cross sections for triton interactions with deuterium and lithium. It has been widely demonstrated that these cross sections are overly pessimistic or, more precisely, completely blind to triton interactions with deuterium and lithium over most of the relevant energy range. As a consequence, the results obtained in this report provide only a limited perspective on what actually occurs, as can be inferred by comparing the $t+d$ cross-section curves—both in the parameterized theoretical version (black) and in the version obtained from experimental data (red)—which are presented both in our report on cross sections dated May 8, 2017 [2] and in Figure 2 of this report. Since the data underlying the red curve have been confirmed by experimental measurements, we can reasonably conclude that, with properly implemented experimental cross sections in the new version of GEANT4, the expectations for the same study could be significantly higher.

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Appendix A Future Studies and Further Investigations

During the execution of this work, which led to the drafting of the three reports:

1. "Study of Neutron Moderation at 14.1 MeV in Beryllium" [3];
2. "Study of Tritium Production and Interactions in LiD" [4];
3. "Study of Deuterium Concentration in Lithium Deuteride: Tritium Fusion on Deuterium" (this report).

as well as the additional report on cross sections [2], several aspects have emerged that could be highly beneficial to explore further:

- **Geometry of the Beryllium Moderator:** In the case of a point-like and isotropic neutron source, the optimal geometry for a moderator is spherical. However, if the neutrons are produced by a tritium-deuterium generator that does not have isotropic emission, it may be interesting to investigate different geometric configurations for the moderator, such as, first among them, the cylindrical configuration;
- **Spectrum at the Output of the Neutron Generator:** The entire study conducted so far is based on the production of monochromatic 14.1 MeV neutrons. However, a real neutron generator will output an energy spectrum with an angular distribution rather than a monochromatic and isotropic line. It would be useful, as soon as the experimental data become available, to input this spectrum into the simulation instead of the monochromatic and isotropic generation currently used;
- **Dissipation of Absorbed Heat:** The beryllium moderator absorbs a large amount of energy (heat) through the neutron thermalization process (elastic neutron-beryllium scattering). The dissipation of this heat necessitates the use of cooling materials, such as water or heavy water, which in turn can act as neutron moderators. The inclusion of such materials in the experimental setup alters the moderation process, which must be accounted for in the simulation. This alteration could affect the characteristics of the beryllium moderator (particularly its thickness);
- **Tritium-Tritium Interaction:** The results obtained in this report indicate that neutron interactions in the fuel produce a large number of tritons, which, not interacting through the various possible channels, remain trapped in the material until they decay (see Figures 4, 5, and 6). This leads to an accumulation of tritons that may make the tritium-tritium interaction non-negligible, warranting further investigation;
- **Be-LiD-D*** Mixture:** In light of the conclusions of this report, using a mixture of lithium deuteride and ultra-dense deuterium provides an advantage in the number of $t+d$ interactions. This consideration suggests the possibility of using mixtures with different concentrations of beryllium, lithium deuteride, and deuterium, instead of employing layers of distinct "pure" materials;
- **Experimental Cross Sections:** As extensively discussed in Section 2.2 on Physics and in the Conclusions of this report, conducting this last phase of the study using the simplified parameterized theoretical cross sections has certainly led to an underestimation of the obtained results. In light of this, it is essential to verify, once the experimental cross sections are correctly implemented in the new version of GEANT4, how the results presented here will change due to this improvement.